

The relative number of qualified medical personnel but not the number of hospital beds influences the life expectancy

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Abstract:

According to universal health coverage (UHC), established by World Health Organisation, all people of all ages should achieve better health and well-being in the field of disease prevention, health promotion, and treatment for communicable and non-communicable diseases. Thus, an urgent need exists to implement improvements in health care services based on sufficient evidence. Life expectancy results from many factors, including health care system regulations and resources.

The aim of the study was to evaluate the influence of the relative number of nurses/midwives, doctors and hospital beds on the life expectancy.

The cross-sectional analysis was based on data from 46 countries reported by World Bank, WHO and Eurostat in years 2015-2016. The correlation between the life expectancy and relative number of nurses/midwives, doctors and hospital beds was evaluated. To trace the differences with regard to life expectancy, analyzed countries were divided into two groups based on life expectancy: <75 years (group 1) and 75-85 years (group 2).

The results are presented in table 1. There were correlations between life expectancy and the relative number of nurses/midwives and doctors ($p < 0.001$, $r = 0.676$, and $p < 0.001$, $r = 0.561$, respectively), but not with the number of hospital beds ($p < 0.797$, $r = 0.261$) The relative number of nurses/midwives and doctors were higher in group 2 compare to group 1 ($p = 0.0016$ and $p = 0.0418$, respectively), but the relative number of hospital bed did not differ between investigated groups.

Keywords:

Medical Life Expectancy, Elderly Life Expectancy, Life Expectancy Without Medical Care, Access To Healthcare, Life Expectancy, Increase Life Expectancy, Life Expectancy Trends

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Biography:

Professor Bozena Czarkowska-Paczek is a head of the Department of Clinical Nursing at the Warsaw Medical University. She also has the position as Deputy Dean of Faculty for Health Science, Nursing Department. She is the member of Polish Accreditation Committee and the head of Medical and Health Science Team since 2013. Prof. Bozena Czarkowska-Paczek has her expertise in nursing, including nursing education and practice, and their role in health care system. She is an author of scientific papers in this field and gave lectures and presentations on international and national congresses.

SRHR issues on advocacy in Pakistan

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Abstract:

Pakistan is one of the patriarchal society where speaking on SRHR to be talk as capsulated taboo among every individual where else it's hard to find proper language or terminology to communicate as it's taken Tobe taboo for that everything belongs to SRHR is hash ! On the other side of the screen, the role of funding and interest of governmental and non-governmental representatives on SRHR is huge sternly the picture is complex where more violence, abuses, morbidity and mortality are at peak which crosses its trash hold to leave the unfolded sabotage of physical, emotional , and mental wellbeing's in surroundings. Furthermore, the usage of knowledge is inappropriate where the height of offensiveness is more empowered then preparedness to be act individual on flight and lights modes appropriately, moreover, the myths and misconception as carried as strong tie knot from generation to be transformed wisely and supremely followed as holy and precious ancestor's calls. The practices are so strong with holding its significance value belief system, which even can deny the modern and evidence based practices effortlessly. However to deal these track trickles one should be phenomenal person with the same community to understand the cultural sensitivity along with inclusion to address on SRHR with this shift of paradigm youth can play vital role to reduce the gender inequality , discrimination , abuses , penetration and crimes in reproductive health care system. The oral presentation will be endeavors based on my community lead volunteer on SRHR across Pakistan to provide the strategies and recommendation and how to create the obstruction, which allow people to approach the right person on right, time to be subsidized from uninviting scenario.

Keywords:

SRHR patriarchal, myths, misconception, abuse, penetration, mental wellbeing, advocacy and cultural inclusion.

Biography:

Public Health Specialist, Global Good Will Ambassador Pakistan, B.A, BScN, RN & RM along with Diploma in Hospital and Health Care Management, she has an enriched experience working as a community health nurse, M&E administrator role, policy developer, ISO 2015 quality assurance audit competency, motivational speaker, master trainer in SRHR, family planning, parents role and relationship, project consultancy, she is bringing her diversified experience from AKDN, Green Star social marketing and other organization, Naurin is active social worker in the community to assist students in career for identifying better scholarships , accommodation, patient welfare, event organizer for arranging health camps and health awareness workshops in the community. However she has published more than 8 publications in National and International journals.

Teaching at Kharadar General Hospital affiliated by Dow University health science taking undergraduate and professional nurses courses. Currently working with UN Migration Health Nurse

Impact Of Nurse Initiated Pre-Operative Counseling On Post Operative Pain And Anxiety

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Abstract:

Patient education/counseling are the most effective strategy used by nurses to empower their patients. Patients hospitalized for surgical interventions usually afraid of the unknown of surgical intervention and the annoying environment of the hospital, thus patient needs physical and psychological preparation before surgical intervention. The process of hospitalization as well as surgery (minor or major) develop and anxiety and stress in patient at the time of admission. Inadequate pre-operative education/counseling lead to increases post-operative outcomes such as pain and anxiety. These two major consequences of surgical intervention leads to a number of complications such as delay recovery, delay resuming of bowel movements, overburden the care giver financially, readmission and even treatment failure. The aim of this study was to test weather pre-operative education/counseling given by nurse has any impact on patient post-operative pain and anxiety level. This was a randomized control trial carried out in surgical department of Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar, Pakistan. Visual analog scale for pain assessment while for anxiety assessment zung anxiety inventory for adult's patients was used for data collection.

Keywords:

Patient education/counseling, alternative therapy, post-operative pain, post-operative anxiety, control group, intervention group.

Biography:

Abdul Wajid, CEO of Prime Institute of Health Science Pakistan. He is the President of Pakistan Private Nursing Institutions. RN .Diploma in CHN, Post Graduate RN, and MBA Hospital Management. He is also group Chairman of Prime Medical Colleges. He is the youngest leader of Nursing. NURSING EDUCATIONEST profession.

Impact Of Nurse Initiated Pre-Operative Counseling On Post Operative Pain And Anxiety

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Abstract:

Patient education/counseling are the most effective strategy used by nurses to empower their patients. Patients hospitalized for surgical interventions usually afraid of the unknown of surgical intervention and the annoying environment of the hospital, thus patient needs physical and psychological preparation before surgical intervention. The process of hospitalization as well as surgery (minor or major) develop and anxiety and stress in patient at the time of admission. Inadequate pre-operative education/counseling lead to increases post-operative outcomes such as pain and anxiety. These two major consequences of surgical intervention leads to a number of complications such as delay recovery, delay resuming of bowel movements, overburden the care giver financially, readmission and even treatment failure. The aim of this study was to test weather pre-operative education/counseling given by nurse has any impact on patient post-operative pain and anxiety level. This was a randomized control trial carried out in surgical department of Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar, Pakistan. Visual analog scale for pain assessment while for anxiety assessment zung anxiety inventory for adult's patients was used for data collection.

Keywords:

Patient education/counseling, alternative therapy, post-operative pain, post-operative anxiety, control group, intervention group.

Biography:

Mehran khan, BSN, MPH, PHD fellow (public health)

Assistant professor, Dean Faculty of Nursing & public health. Expertise in Nursing Leadership & Management, Nursing education & research. Lectures and presentation for professional development of new undergraduate nurses nationwide. Public health expert play a vital role in health education and promotion in community.